

INFLUENCE OF ONLINE TELEVISION STREAMING PLATFORMS ON THE STUDYING HABITS OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN OGUN STATE

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ABSTRACT

Online television streaming platforms has become an integral part of the daily lives of individuals, especially among younger generations, including university students. Students now make up majority of online television streaming viewers, which has an influence on how they live their everyday lives and alter their study habits. Hence this study focused on the influence of online television streaming platforms on the study habits of Private university students in Ogun State. The study adopted a survey research design. The study population consisted of students of Christopher University and Mepherston University. Using the Taro Yamane formula (1967), a sample size of 500 respondents was derived, out of which 494 were returned and validated. The proportional technique and convenient sampling were used to pick respondents in selected universities. A validated questionnaire was used for data collection for the study. Descriptive statistics, frequency distribution, mean standard deviation and linear regression were used to analyze the data collected. Findings from the study showed that online television streaming platforms even though has become very popular among students, it had no negative influence on the study habits of private university students, except in the area of class attendance. The study by way of recommendations advocated for continuous encouragement and enlightenment on positive use of these streaming platforms by students.

Keywords: Online television streaming, study habits, reading, class attendance, time management

Introduction

There is no denial to the fact that online TV streaming, is growing in leaps and bounds among young Nigerians, especially among Millennials and the aptly termed Gen Z. Online TV streaming offers a new and refreshing approach for many people in these generations to keep up with the newest material, including films, news, sports, and other entertainment offerings.

It is not surprising that companies like Netflix, Disney, Ndani TV, and Iroko TV have increased their efforts to target the Nigerian market, which is mostly made up of young people. These competing online streaming providers in Nigeria are constantly offering various incentives, such as one-month free watching packages, in order to attract a greater share of the expanding market of prospective online TV streaming customers (Camilleri & Falzon, 2021).

People, especially youths are not just watching programmes on conventional television sets, but also on mobile devices and Smart TVs that enable them to access mass media information over the Internet. Generally, as observed, students especially at the tertiary level are often influenced by the idea of watching several series and episodes of programmes in one sitting on Netflix (Rubenking et al., 2018). Also, this phenomenon has become more popular among young adults due to the influx of several types of video

content available online and its accessibility globally. The usage of online TV streaming platforms by students is massive no doubt. However, students' academic performance is heavily dependent on the type of study habits adopted, either effective or in-effective.

According to Aryal (2016), students who fail to develop good habits are bound to face various problems and possibly develop negative attitude to study which may lead to poor performance. Also, Bakare (1975), cited in Sunday and Akporehwe (2022), identified bad study habits such as inadequate time allocation for studies, delay or non-completion of assignments, defective examination strategies, defective note-taking and lack of teacher consultation.

Husain (2020), observes that good study habits are essential to educational success; as they contribute to a successful academic future. Given the expanding impact and rising popularity of online television streaming, both domestically and internationally, university students provide a compelling demographic to investigate and a valuable group to examine in the realm of online TV streaming.

Statement of the Problem

The emergence of online television streaming services in Nigeria in recent years has transformed the dimension of programme viewership by students, giving viewers numerous ways to keep up on their favourite shows even while travelling. According to Ugboaja and Anorie (2022), students (youths) represent the enormous majority of consumers of online television streaming contents in Nigeria based on the availability of smart phones and devices.

However, the effect on students' study habits could however be positive or negative. On the positive side, an online streaming platform like YouTube could be used for independent research, watching educational contents and doing assignments. Panda & Pandey (2017), contend that a significant number of students experience stress due to the combined factors, academic challenges, lack of focus, and personal issues.

Thus, binge-watching may serve as a means of alleviating tension caused by such situations. However, some individuals believe that instead of aiding students intellectually, students' involvement on Online TV streaming platforms seems to distract them from reading, focusing in class, doing assignments, and impede their preparation for tests and examinations. This study therefore examines the influence of online television streaming platforms on the studying habits of private university students in Ogun state.

Hypothesis

H0₁: Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the reading habit of private university students in Ogun state

H0₂: Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the class attendance of private university students in Ogun state

H0₃: Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the independent research skills of private university students in Ogun state

H0₄: Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the time management of private university students in Ogun state

Literature Review

Online Television Streaming

Online television streaming refers to online programming that makes content available through a computer screen, tablet or speaker or entails the watching of conventional television obtained over the Internet (Noll, 2004; Ferguson, 2012). According to Ugboaja (2022), online streaming has gained wide popularity across the globe based on its inherent benefits over the traditional medium of watching television shows.

Scholars like Chukwu et. al. (2022), have identified perceived ease of use as one of the core benefits of online streaming because it allows the audience to take charge of their streaming experience without hassle. Atakiti et al. (2017), remarked that online streaming allows users to access any missed programme on the Internet through on-demand streaming and the audience also has the power to adjust the screen picture and sound to suit their desire.

Another benefit of online streaming is its flexibility nature. Users can subscribe to a streaming package, can download and watch the content from any part of the world rather than being limited to content provided by local cable station. According to the 2022 report by Digital TV Research, it is projected that Africa will have 13.72 million SVOD subscriptions by 2027, a significant increase from the 4.89 million subscriptions recorded at the end of 2021 (Miller, 2021; Simon, 2022b).

Streaming in Nigeria is also becoming progressively more popular, especially in urban communities. As of 2022, streaming users in Nigeria are speculated to be around 15% of the 200 million Nigerian population and forecasts predict an increase to around 22% by 2027 (*New Telegraph*, 2022).

Study Habits

Several definitions have been offered to the term “study habit”. For instance, Dayal (2013), sees study habits as well-planned and deliberate pattern of study which has attained a form of consistency on the part of the students towards understanding academic subjects and passing in examination. Aleke (2016), stated that how a student takes his or her studies, greatly determines his/her level of academic achievements.

Based on the foregoing, study habits habit is consistent in nature and portrays habitual practices for studying which can good or bad and effective or ineffective. According to Monu et al. (2020), studying, revolves around attending lectures, laboratories, and libraries, completing assignments, taking notes amongst others. Onwukeme (2023), also affirms that study habit as study routines, include but not restricted to, frequency of studying sessions, review of material, self-testing, rehearsal of learned material, and studying in conducive environment.

According to Chukwu et. al. (2022), study habit is measured by certain parameters which include; the rate at which the learner studies, the depth of what was studied, the manner at which the study was made and the consultations made during the study to enhance the knowledge acquired. A learner might spend much time in studying but might not spend the time in digging deep into the contents being studied.

Another might study sparingly and just paraphrase the work yet conclude that study is done. In a good study habit, all the parameters are expected to be deeply observed. The extent to which students deliberately build and use effective preparation and learning techniques significantly impacts their academic success.

Therefore, the study habit is a significant determinant of students' academic achievement in the classroom. Sunday and Akporehwe (2022), affirmed that good or effective study habits facilitate retention of concept and enable students to spend their time more productively and efficiently while bad or ineffective study habits inhibit understanding of concepts.

Online Television Streaming and Study Habits

The transition to digital platforms for education and employment has posed difficulties for individuals in terms of focus and efficiency. Students are now more vulnerable to distractions as digital media platforms like YouTube and Instagram are just a click away (Gillick & Magoulas, 2020). Factors such as lack of interest, motivation to learn and indiscipline are affecting online classes (Muthuprasad et al., 2021).

Excessive television viewing, intense TV consumption, and addiction to television have all been associated with negative effects on the physical health, emotional well-being, social relationships, and academic performance of college students. The prevalent habit of binge-watching has lately prompted concerns over potential adverse effects.

Thus, it is important to raise students' consciousness about the negative effects of binge television viewing by introducing prevention and training programs to help mitigate these effects (Dandamudi & Sathiyaseelan, 2018). Rusz et al. (2020), found that platforms like Netflix avert students' attention from their academics. Nevertheless, Vaterlaus et al. (2019), report that some students motivate themselves to complete work quickly in order to binge-watch content afterwards as a reward.

However, there are several drawbacks to these platforms. Meier et al., (2016) explored the phenomenon of 'Facebocrastination', leading to procrastination of academic tasks and sleep by students. Watching movies late night gives a good feeling. Well-being is important for students to lead happy lives. Farrukh et al. (2021) reported negative correlation between media consumption and students' well-being and academic achievement. Since academics forms a major part of students' lives, it is important to understand their attitude and approach. According to Barton et al., (2018), attention and motivation are significant predictors of academic performance.

Theoretical Framework

The uses and gratification theory is the theoretical framework utilised for this study. Drawing on decades of study in mass communication, Katz, Blumler and Gurevitch first proposed the uses and gratifications theory in 1974. The original focus of the idea was on the reasons why people choose to watch or listen to certain types of mass media material, with an emphasis on human choice, usage, and satisfaction.

Amiri et al. (2012), Agbim et al. (2023) stated that the uses and gratifications theory focuses on how consumers seek media and how satisfied they are with the media kind, content, and mode of consumption. The theory focuses on how and why people use the media to satisfy their needs. The basic assumption of this theory is that, media users have control over their media usage and that, users play active role in interpreting and integrating media into their own lives.

The theory of uses and gratifications offers a clearer picture of why individuals adopt new media technologies and what they gain from doing so. As a result, this theory is pertinent to this study because it explains how media audiences select from a wide range of options for how to watch television and follow up with their favourite programmes, particularly using various devices.

Thanks to internet television streaming, viewers have more control over their media consumption and may actively participate in the utilisation of new media technologies into their everyday routines and habits. This theory therefore provides a powerful framework with which students use the online media to meet their specific needs and what students do with online television streaming platforms. Students are more likely to use an online television streaming platform if it effectively gratifies the need they are seeking to fulfill.

Methodology

This study used a survey research design, while questionnaire was used in getting data from the respondents. The population for this study consists of 2106 students of two selected universities (Christopher University and McPherson University). The two universities were selected to make comparisons between what obtains in a faith based private university and one that is not faith based. Using the Taro Yamane formula (1967), a sample size of five hundred (500) was derived. The equation is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Christopher University

$$n = \frac{306}{1 + 306(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{306}{1 + 306(0.0025)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{306}{1 + 0.765}$$

$$n = \frac{306}{1.765}$$

$$n = 173$$

McPherson University

$$n = \frac{1800}{1 + 1800(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1800}{1 + 1800(0.025)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1800}{1 + 4.5}$$

$$n = \frac{1800}{5.5}$$

$$n = 327$$

Therefore, 173 + 327 = 500

Convenient sampling was used to pick respondents in the selected universities. Five hundred (500) copies of the questionnaire were distributed, while four hundred and ninety-four (494) copies were retrieved from the respondents and validated for further studies, resulting in an approximately 98.8% per cent response rate.

The 28-item questionnaire was broken into six sections. Section one contained three demographic data points. Section two consisted of five (5) items that intended to gather information regarding exposure to Online television streaming platforms, while sections three to six consisted of five (5) items each which were developed from each of the research questions.

Reliability and Validity of Research Instruments

The reliability of the research instrument for this study was established by the Composite Cronbach's alpha values for the questionnaire, which were judged to be good based on the pilot study findings. The reliability scores for the four items in the questionnaire are as follows: 0.958 (96%), 0.921 (92%), 0.95 (95%), and 0.91 (91%). Face and construct validity were used to validate the study instrument with the help of experts on the questionnaire. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were applied to summarise and present the data. Additionally, inferential statistical methods, such as regression analysis conducted with SPSS, were used to explore the relationships between variables and to test the research hypotheses.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Test of Hypotheses

The research hypothesis is tested at 0.05 on the Influence of online television streaming platforms on the studying habits of private university students in Ogun state:

H0₁: Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the reading habit of private university students in Ogun state.

Table 1a ANOVA & Model Summary for the Test of Significant Influence of Online television streaming platforms on the reading habit of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Sum Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	3.284	1	3.284	.217	0.642^b
Residual	7453.643	492	15.144		
Total	7453.927	493			

R= .021

R Square = .000

Adjusted R Square = -.002

Table 1b Linear Regression Testing Significant Influence of online television streaming platforms on reading habits of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	14.742	.606		24.344	.000
Online TV Streaming	.037	.079	.021	.466	.642

Dependent Variable: Reading Habit

Table 1 shows that online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the reading habit of private university students in Ogun state with p. value at ($\beta = .021$, $t = 24.344$, $p > 0.05$). This suggests that the reading habit of the students of the selected private university is not affected by the online television streaming platform.

Therefore, given the p. value (.642), the hypothesis that online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the reading habit of private university students in Ogun state was here accepted.

H₀₂: Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the class attendance of private university students in Ogun state

Table 2a ANOVA & Model Summary for the Test of Significant Influence of Online television streaming platforms on the class attendance of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Sum Squares	<i>Df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Regression	122.084	1	122.084	8.495	.004^b
Residual	7070.305	492	14.371		
Total	7192.389	493			

R= 0.130^a

R Square = 0.017

Adjusted R Square = 0.15

Table 2b Linear Regression Testing Significant Influence of online television streaming platforms on class attendance of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	12.520	.590		21.224	.000
Online TV Streaming	.223	.077	.130	2.915	.004

Dependent Variable: Class Attendance

Table 2 shows that online television streaming platforms have a significant influence on the class attendance of private university students in Ogun state ($\beta = .130$, $t = 12.224$, $p < 0.05$). This implies that online television streaming platform had significant influence on the class attendance of private university students in Ogun state. Hence, given the p. value (.004), the hypothesis that Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the class attendance of private university students in Ogun state was rejected.

H₀₃: Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the independent research skills of private university students in Ogun state

Table 3a ANOVA & Model Summary for the Test of Significant Influence of Online television streaming platforms on the independent research skills of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Sum Squares	<i>Df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Regression	486	1	.486	.030	.863^b
Residual	8075.223	492	16.413		
Total	8075.709	493			

R= .008^a

R Square = .000

Adjusted R Square = .002

Table 3b Linear Regression Testing Significant Influence of online television streaming platforms on independent research skill of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	16.872	.630		26.762	.000
Online TV Streaming	.014	.082	.008	.172	.863

Dependent Variable: Research skill

Table 3 shows that online television streaming platforms does not have a significant influence on the independent research skills of private university students in Ogun state ($\beta=.008$, $t = 26.762$, $p>0.05$). Hence, given the p. value (.863), the hypothesis that Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the independent research skill of private university students in Ogun state was accepted.

H₀₄: Online television streaming Platforms does not significantly influence the time management of private university students in Ogun state

Table 4a ANOVA & Model Summary for the Test of Significant Influence of Online television streaming platforms on the time management of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Sum Squares	<i>Df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Regression	5.944	1	5.944	.0334	.564^b
Residual	8693.109	488	17.814		
Total	8699.53	489			

R= .026^a

R Square = .001

Adjusted R Square = -.001

Table 4b Linear Regression Testing Significant Influence of online television streaming platforms on time management of private university students in Ogun state

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	15.685	.658		23.836	.000
Online TV Streaming	.049	.085	.026	-.578	.564

Dependent Variable: Time management

Table 4 shows that online television streaming platforms does not have a significant influence on the time management of private university students in Ogun state ($\beta=.026$, $t= 23.836$, $p>0.05$). This implies that online television streaming platform had no significant influence on the time management of private university students in Ogun state. Hence, given the p. value (.664), the hypothesis that Online television streaming platforms does not significantly influence the time management of private university students in Ogun state was accepted.

Discussion of findings

The major aim of this study was to investigate the influence of online television streaming platforms on the studying habits of private university students in Ogun state. The first objective was to determine the influence of online television streaming platforms on the reading habits of private university students in Ogun State. Findings from the study indicate that online television streaming platforms has no direct impact on the reading habits of private university students.

This is evident from the mean responses of the parameters used in the study. All of the mean responses fell below 3.5, suggesting a strong disagreement among the respondents. This suggests that respondents do not find it difficult to concentrate on reading and streaming online television programmes simultaneously. This implies that once students have good study habits, they can easily avoid distractions.

This is in line with the position of Mark and Howard (2019), that the most common challenge to the success of students in all ramifications is a lack of effective or positive (good) study habit. This position is further reinforced by Sunday and Akporehwe (2022), when they affirmed that good or effective study habits facilitate retention of concept and enable students to spend their time more productively and efficiently while bad or ineffective study habits inhibit understanding of concepts.

The second objective was to determine the influence of online television streaming platforms on the class attendance of private university students in Ogun State. Findings from the study indicate that online television streaming platforms affect their class attendance. This was evident from the linear regression analysis ($\beta= .130$, $t= 12.224$, $p<0.05$). Additionally, the specific statements provided, such as "I can miss a class lecture if I am streaming something very interesting online" and "I rather stream online than attend online lectures," further supported the participants' agreement with the statement.

This is at variance with the position of Emievil (2013), that attendance is essential for every course, particularly for topics such as accounting and statistics. Except if the student has exceptional intelligence and can effortlessly review the teacher's or classmates' notes to comprehend the lesson. The optimal approach is to directly listen to the teacher's words and independently read all the information presented on the board. Non-attendance of courses by the student may result in a limited comprehension of the subject matter.

The third objective was to determine the influence of online television streaming platforms on the independent research skills of private university students in Ogun State. The study found out that the

majority of the participants do not agree that online television streaming platforms have a significant impact on their independent research skills. This deviates from the findings of Oladeji (2019), who examined the influence of social media learning platforms on undergraduates' study habit in basic science education in Nigerian universities. The result showed that there was a significant effect on the students' study habits after being exposed to social media learning platforms.

Also, a significant portion of the participants in this study use online television platforms like YouTube for their assignments and believe that these platforms help in improving their communication skills and learning new creative skills, which is in line with the findings of Kemal et. al (2023), that students who engage in watching entertainment programs have worse academic performance compared to those who watch instructional programs.

This is in line with the assumptions of the uses and gratifications theory which provides a framework with which students use the online media to meet their specific needs and what students do with online television streaming platforms. Students are more likely to use an online television streaming platform if it effectively gratifies the need they are seeking to fulfill.

The fourth objective was to determine the influence of online television streaming platforms on time management among private university students in Ogun State. Some students don't know how to manage their time; they accommodate everything that comes their way even the ones that intercept their studies. Also, according to Sunday and Akporehwe (2022), poor time management was identified as one of the bad study habits which may affect students' academic performances.

Findings from the study however showed that the majority of the participants do not agree that online television streaming platforms have a significant impact on their time management skills. The average weighted mean of the participants responses was 3.06, indicating a general disagreement with the statement. Specifically, the majority of the participants preferred to spend their productive time reading books at night rather than streaming online television programmes.

Conclusion

The study examined the influence of online television streaming platforms on the studying habits of private university students in Ogun state. Findings from the study revealed that online television streaming platforms even though has become very popular among private university students in Ogun state, it had no negative influence on the study habits of private university students, except in the area of class attendance. The study therefore recommends that instead of students obsessing or abusing online television streaming platforms, they should engender the benefits of online television streaming platforms and moderately apply into their daily lives.

Limitation of the study

Studying habits of students could be affected by a plethora of factors. However, this study was only limited to the influence of online television streaming platforms, further studies could examine other possible factors that may affect the studying habits of students.

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